

Modelling and strategies for the assessment and **Optimisation** of **Energy Usage** aspects of rail innovation

Deliverable D 3.4

S2R innovation second periodic assessment

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Report contributors		
<i>Name</i>	<i>Beneficiary Short Name</i>	<i>Details of contribution</i>
L. Pröhl	UROS	Author
H. Aschemann	UROS	Review
M. Marsilla	STAV	Review, Verification of calculations, Alignment with D5.2
H. Dittus	DLR (FINE1)	Review

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1 Executive Summary

This deliverable ‘DO3.4 - S2R innovation second periodic assessment’ is the third part of a three-part deliverable series DO3.3 and DO3.4, which focuses on the periodic assessment of the technical innovations within OPEUS and Shift2Rail. This third part of the deliverable report builds upon the reported investigations and technical approaches, within single technical demonstrators (TD’s) of Shift2Rail. The data regarding the technical investigations are gathered within the framework of the EU-project FINE1, see [1]. The main objective of this report is providing an overview and analysis for the investigated innovations of the gathered innovations.

In analogy to the first and second part of this report (see [2] and [3]), the analysis is based on simulation results, which are determined with the OPEUS-tool (developed within OPEUS WP2 “Simulation model and tool development”, see [4], [5]).

To enable a proper assessment of the technical innovations, the arising simulation results are compared to the baseline scenario simulations. These baseline scenarios are described in [6] and [7] and the baseline simulation results are evaluated in [8]. Based on these comparisons, the potential of the investigated innovations is discussed.

This report serves as an input for WP 7, which has the objective to provide a summary as well as a global vision of energy usage in railway applications. Furthermore, this report is linked to OPEUS WP 5, which includes a sensitivity analysis for several train parameters regarding energy consumption. The current report allows for backing up this sensitivity analysis in order to provide several simulation evaluation for improved train characteristics.

Additionally, the outcomes of this report are expected to support the work in WP4 of FINE1 in order to provide an opportunity to analyse the investigated techniques as well as to determine the focus of further investigations.

2 Abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation / Acronyms	Description
FINE1	Shift2Rail partner project: Future Improvement for Energy and Noise – Grant Agreement number: 730818
FrMain	Freight Mainline service
HS300	High Speed service, maximum speed: 300km/h
HS250	High Speed service, maximum speed: 250km/h
IC	Intercity service
Reg160	Regional service, maximum speed: 160km/h
Reg140	Regional service, maximum speed: 140km/h
Suburb	Suburban service
TD	Technical demonstrator
WP	Work package

3 Background

The present document constitutes the third part of the three-part deliverable series of DO3.3 and DO3.4 in the framework of WP3, task 3.2 (Scenario simulations) of OPEUS project (S2R-OC-CCA-02-2015).

The data sets describing the technical improvements of the Shift2Rail technical demonstrators are gathered within WP4 of the FINE1 project, see [1].

Furthermore, this report contributes to WP5 and WP7 of OPEUS as well as to WP4 of FINE1.

4 Objective/Aim

This document has been prepared to provide an overview for assessing the innovations of the Shift2Rail technical demonstrators as well as to present the corresponding simulation results and energy consumptions.

The results presented in the current deliverable serve as a periodic analysis of the work done within OPEUS WP 3, task 3.2 (Scenario Simulations).

5 Introduction

The objective of WP3 is the evaluation of energy simulations for various predefined scenarios regarding the rolling stock. Those simulations serve as a reliable baseline for the assessment of technical innovations regarding energy consumptions and energy savings.

To perform these energy simulations, the OPEUS-tool was developed within OPEUS WP2 “Simulation model and tool development” (see [4], [5]). This tool enables a user to calculate the energy consumption for various trains, tracks and operating scenarios. It uses a backward simulation approach to determine the required power profiles according to a given speed profile. These power profiles will be determined for single components of the traction chain (e.g. power profile at the motor level, power profile at the transformer level) as well as for the total power profile at the energy delivery point. The simulations presented in this deliverable are evaluated with OPEUS-tool version 7.

This current report is the third part of a three-part deliverable series, which provides a periodic assessment of the technical innovations. This third part of the deliverable series focuses on the evaluation of simulations covering the technical innovations achieved by the Shift2Rail technical demonstrators. To allow for an assessment of the innovations, the simulation results are compared to a reference scenario. This baseline is presented in detail in [8].

To enable a better understanding, however, the reference scenario is described and the simulation results are briefly summarized in section 6.

The main objective of section 7 is the presentation of an analysis of the simulation results for improved weight characteristics of the trains. In addition, section 7.2 focuses on analysing the effect of increased efficiencies for the components of the traction chain.

6 Summary of the reference scenarios

The objective of this section is to provide a summary of the predefined reference scenarios, which serve as a baseline for the periodic assessment.

The definition of the reference scenarios, which determines the track characteristics, the train parameters as well as further boundary conditions for the simulation are provided in [6] and [7]. A detailed presentation of the energy simulation results of these baseline scenarios is given in [8].

In order to enable a clear understanding of these reference scenarios, the following paragraphs recap the main energy results determined as well as the most important boundary conditions, required for the executed energy simulations.

Table 1 provides a summary of the most important boundary conditions for the baseline scenario simulations. The reference energy consumption is determined, hence, based on these characteristics. Notably, this table defines the trajectory mode as well as the operating strategy regarding the utilisation of traction components for small loads. Another specification for the baseline scenario is the determination of the considered season. According to the definition of the train parameters (see [7] and [9]), the seasons influence the defined auxiliary load power. The working group agreed to implement the spring/autumn seasons for the baseline simulations.

Baseline scenario characteristic	
Track data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> According to the agreed service profiles (see [6], [7])
Train data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> According to the defined parameter sets According to the defined efficiency maps } see [6]
ESS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No ESS (see [7])
Traction components	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Induction motor IGBT converter Common transformer } see [6]
Environmental conditions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No head wind No influence of the ambient temperature } see [6]
Trajectory mode	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Coasting enabled – refer to the green curve in Figure 1: Generic driving cycle (exceptions possible!): <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Acceleration with max. acceleration (limited by the max. traction effort and passenger comfort) until the speed limit is reached Cruising (const. speed), if necessary Coasting to fulfill the time table Braking with max. deceleration (limited by the max. braking effort and passenger comfort)

Figure 1: Possible trajectory modes

Operating strategy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No load distribution between single traction drives No partial switch-offs of single traction drives
Auxiliary connection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Auxiliary load is connected to the DC intermediate circuit for all service categories
Season mode	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Simulations for spring/autumn and summer/winter seasons Documented in detail for the spring/autumn case Documented result overview at least on the same level as KPI (kWh/km) for both (spring/autumn, summer/winter) cases

Table 1: Boundary conditions for the simulation of the baseline scenario (see [8])

The basic criterion to assess the influence of technical innovations is the total energy consumption of the railway vehicle. Within OPEUS, this consists of the total amount of energy, consumed by the vehicle during one drive cycle for one of the predefined service routes. The OPEUS-tool enables a user to determine the total consumed energy at the catenary E_{cons} as well as the energy recuperated to the catenary E_{rec} . To have only one energy value for the assessment of the energy consumption, the total net energy budget is determined by:

$$E_{net} = E_{cons} - E_{rec}. \quad (7.1)$$

Table 2 states the basic simulation results for each predefined service category, determined with the OPEUS-tool V7, using the trajectory mode timetable with coasting as indicated in Figure 1. The total energy budget E_{net} is emphasised by the double-framed column.

The value within the last column of Table 2 represents the energy consumption of the total synthetic trains for one driven km on the predefined track. This enables an easier comparison and analysis of the single service categories. For more simulation results and analysis of the reference scenarios the reader is referred to [8]*.

* Note: Deviations between the Table 2 and the reference values within [8] are caused by the usage of different versions of the OPEUS-tool.

	<i>total time</i>	<i>total distance</i>	<i>commercial speed</i>	<i>traction energy at the wheel</i>	<i>total braking energy at the wheel</i>	<i>consumed energy at the catenary</i>	<i>recuperated energy at the catenary</i>	<i>net energy budget E_{net}</i>	<i>consumption per km**</i>
Unit	h	km	km/h	kWh	kWh	kWh	kWh	kWh	Wh/km
HS300	01:50:00	300	164	3502	152	5136	80*	5056*	16851*
HS250	02:06:00	300	143	2850*	655*	4414*	220*	4194*	13979*
Intercity	02:42:00	250	93	1242*	309*	2274*	191*	2083*	8329*
Reg160	03:00:00	250	83	724*	171*	1560*	117	1453*	5811*
Reg140	01:11:00	70	59	258	137	572*	88*	484*	6917*
Suburb	00:44:00	40	55	430*	293*	723*	204*	520*	12981*
Metro	00:38:00	21.5	34	251*	219*	420*	151*	268*	12466*
Tram	00:29:40	10,7	22	29	23	69	15	54	5031
Freight Mainline	04:20:15	300	69	4129*	736*	5741*	486*	5254*	17514*

*updated baseline values relating to [8]
 **consumption per km is calculated with non-rounded values
 Note: Baseline simulation results are determined with OPEUS tool V6c

Table 2: Total energy consumption of reference scenario simulations

7 Simulative evaluation of technical innovations

The main objective of this section is the presentation of simulation results, w.r.t. the implemented technical innovations that have been gathered by FINE1.

Subsection 7.1 covers simulations regarding possible weight reductions, as subsection 7.2 focus on the improvement of efficiencies of single traction components. A combination of weight and efficiency improvement is investigated in subsection 7.3.

7.1 Improvements of weight characteristics

The current section focuses on the evaluation of simulation results regarding improved weight characteristics. As a decreased weight also allows for higher acceleration (as long as the acceleration/braking is not limited by operating boundaries e.g. passenger comfort), the speed profiles for the trains will be slightly adjusted. Figure 2 shows the effect of higher acceleration and deceleration limits in a schematic way.

Figure 2: Schematic trajectory profiles with lower and higher accelerations

As emphasized in Figure 2, the possibility of an increased acceleration allows for different trajectory profiles, e.g., with a higher amount of coasting.

Therefore, the results presented within this section are based either on the baseline speed profile, or on the updated speed profile with higher accelerations, depending on which profile causes more benefit regarding the total energy consumption.

As mentioned before, the data acquisition was done in the framework of WP4 in FINE1. The gathered data regarding a weight reduction is summarized in Table 3. The main weight reduction is contributed by the car body shell, a decreased weight of the braking system and a decreased mass of the doors. For more details regarding the data gathering, please refer to [1].

Table 3: Simulated weight reductions for different service categories

	HS300	HS250	IC	Reg160	Reg140	Metro	Tram
Assumed coaches	8	8	5	4	4	4	5
Assumed doors	16	16	20	32	32	48	12
Reduced weight per train for car body shell (TD 1.3)	10t	10t	-	-	-	-	-
Reduced weight per coach for improved brakes (TD 1.5)	0,05 t						
Reduced weight per door for lighter doors (TD 1.6)	20 kg	20 kg	17.8 kg	17.8 kg	17.8 kg	16.2 kg	14.5 kg
Baseline weight	450 t	450 t	280 t	142 t	142 t	192 t	41 t
Reduced weight	439,3 t	439,3 t	273,6 t	141,2 t	141,1 t	191 t	40,6 t
Total weight reduction	10,7 t	10,7 t	0,61 t	0,77 t	0,77 t	0,98 t	0,42 t
Relative weight reduction $\frac{m_{base}}{m_{red}}$	2,38%	2,38%	0,22%	0,54%	0,51%	0,51%	1,03%

As the largest mass reduction is achievable for the high speed service, the simulation results are presented in more detail in Table 4 and Table 5. Here, the power profiles at the catenary for the HS300 service are depicted in Figure 3 and Figure 4. As expected, the highest differences between the baseline power profile and the power profile related to the mass reduction are observed for high speeds – leading to high power requests.

For the HS250 service, also the already mentioned property of an additional coasting effects the energy consumption. Due to higher accelerations, the amount of coasting for the last station-to-station drive slightly increases – see Figure 5 and Figure 7. This effect is emphasized in Figure 6 and Figure 7, which show the resulting power profile at the catenary.

Table 4: Simulation results for the improved weight characteristic for HS300 service

Figure 3: Power profile at the catenary for HS300 service

Figure 4: Power profile at the catenary for HS300 service for $t = 2050 \dots 5050$ s

	Energy consumption [kWh] - baseline	Energy consumption [kWh] – reduced weight
Total net energy in kWh	5055	5040
Total energy savings in kWh		15
Total energy savings in %		~0.3

Table 5: Simulation results for the improved weight characteristic for HS250 service

Figure 5: Velocity trajectory for HS250 service

Figure 6: Power profile at the catenary for HS250 service

Figure 7: Detailed speed and power profile for $t = 6000 \dots 7000s$

	Energy consumption [kWh] - baseline	Energy consumption [kWh] – reduced weight
Total net energy	4194	4141
Total energy savings in kWh	53	
Total energy savings in %	~1.25	

The mass improvements of the other service categories do not result in meaningful differences between the power profiles. Nevertheless, the simulated energy results indicate possible energy savings. The energy savings are considered at different levels of the traction chain – at the wheel

level, at the intermediate circuit and at the energy source. These simulated energy values and energy savings for the single service categories are summarized within Table 6 - Table 12.

Table 6: Simulation results for improved weight for HS300 service

	HS300- baseline	HS300 – weight update	Absolute energy difference in kWh	Relative energy difference in %
traction energy at the wheel in kWh	3502,63	3499,11	3,52	0,10
total braking energy at the wheel in kWh	153,59	149,92	3,67	2,39
traction energy of motor converters at DC link in kWh	4015,80	4003,87	11,93	0,30
recuperated energy of motor converters at DC link in kWh	100,04	100,04	0,00	0,00
auxiliary energy at the DC link in kWh	553,08	552,78	0,30	0,06
consumed energy at the catenary in kWh	5135,92	5120,54	15,38	0,30
recuperated energy at the catenary in kWh	80,89	80,89	0,00	0,00
net energy in kWh	5055,03	5039,65	15,38	0,30

Table 7: Simulation results for improved weight for HS250 service

	HS250 – baseline	HS250 – weight update	Absolute energy difference in kWh	Relative energy difference in %
traction energy at the wheel in kWh	2850,94	2794,77	56,17	1,97
total braking energy at the wheel in kWh	654,71	594,49	60,23	9,20
traction energy of motor converters at DC link in kWh	3380,08	3316,71	63,37	1,87
recuperated energy of motor converters at DC link in kWh	273,00	251,53	21,47	7,87
auxiliary energy at the DC link in kWh	598,43	595,76	2,67	0,45
consumed energy at the catenary in kWh	4413,89	4343,61	70,28	1,59
recuperated energy at the catenary in kWh	219,96	202,30	17,66	8,03
net energy in kWh	4193,92	4141,30	52,62	1,25

Table 8: Simulation results for improved weight for Intercity service

	Intercity – baseline	Intercity – weight update	Absolute energy difference in kWh	Relative energy difference in %
traction energy at the wheel in kWh	1242,41	1241,04	1,37	0,11
total braking energy at the wheel in kWh	308,61	308,22	0,39	0,13
traction energy of motor converters at DC link in kWh	1529,10	1528,02	1,07	0,07
recuperated energy of motor converters at DC link in kWh	246,98	246,71	0,27	0,11
auxiliary energy at the DC link in kWh	530,51	530,41	0,10	0,02
consumed energy at the catenary in kWh	2273,72	2272,28	1,44	0,06
recuperated energy at the catenary in kWh	191,37	191,19	0,18	0,09
net energy in kWh	2082,35	2081,10	1,26	0,06

Table 9: Simulation results for improved weight for Regional 160 service

	Reg160 – baseline	Reg160 – weight update	Absolute energy difference in kWh	Relative energy difference in %
traction energy at the wheel in kWh	724,23	723,38	0,85	0,12
total braking energy at the wheel in kWh	172,35	169,89	2,45	1,42
traction energy of motor converters at DC link in kWh	941,76	939,25	2,51	0,27
recuperated energy of motor converters at DC link in kWh	139,95	138,02	1,93	1,38
auxiliary energy at the DC link in kWh	453,85	453,80	0,05	0,01
consumed energy at the catenary in kWh	1559,94	1556,93	3,01	0,19
recuperated energy at the catenary in kWh	107,39	105,77	1,62	1,51
net energy in kWh	1452,55	1451,17	1,39	0,10

Table 10: Simulation results for improved weight for Regional 140 service

	Reg140 – baseline	Reg140 – weight update	Absolute energy difference in kWh	Relative energy difference in %
traction energy at the wheel in kWh	257,74	257,06	0,68	0,26
total braking energy at the wheel in kWh	136,94	136,24	0,70	0,51
traction energy of motor converters at DC link in kWh	332,23	330,84	1,39	0,42
recuperated energy of motor converters at DC link in kWh	111,51	111,02	0,49	0,44
auxiliary energy at the DC link in kWh	179,23	179,19	0,04	0,02
consumed energy at the catenary in kWh	572,10	570,46	1,64	0,29
recuperated energy at the catenary in kWh	87,59	87,17	0,42	0,48
net energy in kWh	484,51	483,29	1,22	0,25

Table 11: Simulation results for improved weight for Metro service

	Metro – baseline	Metro – weight update	Absolute energy difference in kWh	Relative energy difference in %
traction energy at the wheel in kWh	251,32	250,51	0,82	0,32
total braking energy at the wheel in kWh	218,71	217,86	0,84	0,39
traction energy of motor converters at DC link in kWh	313,80	312,73	1,07	0,34
recuperated energy of motor converters at DC link in kWh	170,14	170,14	0,00	0,00
auxiliary energy at the DC link in kWh	114,19	114,17	0,01	0,01
consumed energy at the catenary in kWh	419,57	418,44	1,13	0,27
recuperated energy at the catenary in kWh	151,52	151,52	0,00	0,00
net energy in kWh	268,06	266,93	1,13	0,42

Table 12: Simulation results for improved weight for Tram service

	Tram – baseline	Tram – weight update	Absolute energy difference in kWh	Relative energy difference in %
traction energy at the wheel in kWh	28,86	28,67	0,19	0,64
total braking energy at the wheel in kWh	22,97	22,79	0,18	0,78
traction energy of motor converters at DC link in kWh	38,67	38,42	0,25	0,66
recuperated energy of motor converters at DC link in kWh	18,87	18,72	0,15	0,80
auxiliary energy at the DC link in kWh	33,33	33,33	0,00	0,01
consumed energy at the catenary in kWh	68,57	68,31	0,26	0,38
recuperated energy at the catenary in kWh	14,74	14,59	0,15	0,99
net energy in kWh	53,83	53,72	0,11	0,21

Based on the mass improvements, energy savings in the range of 0.06% (IC service) and approx. 1.25% (HS service) are achievable. As for single train categories different mass improvements are investigated, the ratio between the resulting energy differences and the mass improvement are presented in Figure 8. This allows for a basic assessment of the influence of a mass reduction on possible energy savings. More details on the sensitivity analysis regarding a mass reduction is presented in [10], where impact in energy consumption of +/- 10% variation of the tare mass for the different rail vehicles services were evaluated.

Figure 8: Ratios of resulting energy differences and mass reductions

The high energy saving for the HS250 service is based on the different speed profile which allows for a higher amount of coasting (see Table 5).

7.2 Improvements of efficiency characteristics

Another major pillar for the development of future trains are improvements of single component efficiencies. Both the traction component efficiency and the efficiency of the auxiliaries have a major impact on the total energy consumption.

Deliverable 5.2 (see [10]) has shown that in the case of DC rail vehicles (tram and metro) the traction motor represents the majority of the energy losses, while for AC rail vehicles, most of the energy losses are due to the traction motor and the transformer. However, in this deliverable no improvement on the traction motor energy efficiency map has been evaluated, but other traction components are considered, as it was the innovation data coming from FINE1 (see [1]). Therefore, for this report, especially improved efficiencies of the motor converters and line converters as well as of the transformers (Figure 9, blue components) are under investigation in subsection 7.2.1. Furthermore, the effect of an improved gearbox efficiency (Figure 9, yellow component) for the HS300 and HS250 service are analysed in subsection 0.

Figure 9: Scheme for default traction chain for AC power supply

7.2.1 Improvement of traction component efficiencies

This subsection focuses on improvements regarding the efficiencies of the motor converter, of the line converter as well as of the transformer. The considered efficiency improvements can be achieved by an innovative development of the converters, e.g., by the utilization of SiC-semiconductors. The improved efficiency characteristics, which represent the basis for the following simulations, are summarized in Figure 10, Figure 11 and Figure 12.

Figure 10: Motor converter efficiency maps - baseline vs. update

Figure 11: Line converter efficiency maps - baseline vs. update

Figure 12: Transformer efficiency maps - baseline vs. update

7.2.1.1 Improvement of traction component efficiencies for AC traction topology

To assess the impact of the improved efficiency on the AC power supply, simulations are performed for the HS250, the Reg140 and for the Freight Mainline service.

As the OPEUS-tool allows for logging both the input as well as the output power characteristics (P_{in} resp. P_{out}) for the single components, it is possible to analyse the mean energy efficiency of the single component for the simulated drive cycle according to

$$\eta^E = \frac{E_{out}}{E_{in}} = \frac{\int_0^{t_{end}} P_{out} dt}{\int_0^{t_{end}} P_{in} dt},$$

With E_{out} and E_{in} are the total input and output energy of the component as t_{end} denotes the total driving time.

To give an impression of the overall energy efficiency improvement, the total energy efficiency for the traction chain η_{trac} is determined by multiplying the single component energy efficiencies:

$$\eta_{trac}^E = \eta_{gb}^E \cdot \eta_{mot}^E \cdot \eta_{mot,inv}^E \cdot \eta_{abs,cir}^E \cdot \eta_{lineinv}^E \cdot \eta_{trans}^E.$$

Here, η_{gb}^E denotes the energy efficiency of the gearbox, whereas η_{mot}^E , $\eta_{mot,inv}^E$, $\eta_{abs,cir}^E$, $\eta_{lineinv}^E$ and η_{trans}^E denotes the energy efficiencies of the motor, the motor inverter, the absorption circuit, the line converter as well as of the transformer. The mentioned energy efficiencies as well as the according updates are summarized in Table 13.

However, it is important to mention that the energy efficiency η_{trac}^E only considers the traction chain components. Therefore, the auxiliaries have to be considered as well to determine the energy efficiency η_{total}^E of the total energy conversion, see Figure 13. Here, the total energy efficiency η_{total}^E is defined by the total net energy E_{net} (the energy consumption at the energy source), the positive traction energy at the wheel E_{trac} as well as the auxiliary energy request E_{aux} . Conclusively, the total train energy efficiency is given with

$$\eta_{total}^E = \frac{E_{trac} + E_{aux}}{E_{net}}.$$

Figure 13: Definition of the traction chain efficiency η_{trac} and the total efficiency η_{total}

Table 13: Efficiency values η_{trac} of the traction chain for the simulated drive cycles for the updated traction components for AC power supply

Service category Efficiency of the components	HS250-baseline	HS250 – efficiency update	Reg140 baseline	Reg140 – efficiency update	FrMain baseline	FrMain – efficiency update
Gearbox	0,98	0,98	0,97	0,97	0,98	0,98
Motor	0,851	0,851	0,64	0,64	0,842	0,842
Motor inverter	0,98	0,989	0,954	0,974	0,978	0,987
Absorption circuit	0,977	0,977	0,97	0,97	0,975	0,975
Line converter	0,978	0,995	0,967	0,984	0,974	0,994
Transformer	0,924	0,933	0,879	0,917	0,922	0,9325
Total traction chain energy efficiency η_{trac}^E	0,723	0,749	0,57	0,605	0,707	0,737
Total train energy efficiency η_{total}^E	0,605	0,645	0,616	0,675	0,662	0,69
updated values						

For the services involving an AC traction topology, the power profiles at the catenary are presented in Figure 14 - Figure 16. In these figures, the baseline power profile is compared with the power profile resulting from the increased efficiency. The compared power characteristics indicate that the energy savings based on the efficiency improvements enable a lower power request for the total drive cycle. Obviously, the highest energy savings are obtained during high power request in acceleration and braking phases. Nevertheless, also during coasting – especially at high speed – the updated power profile indicates a benefit of the increased efficiencies.

Figure 14: Power at the energy source for updated efficiency of traction components for the HS250 service

Figure 15: Power at the energy source for updated efficiency of traction components for the Reg140 service

Figure 16: Power at the energy source for updated efficiency of traction components for the Freight Mainline service

In the following, simulation results are presented regarding the energy consumption and energy savings for the total drive cycle. As the efficiency adaptation has no effect on the energy request at the wheel, the following results are only summarized for the DC intermediate level as well as for the energy source level. Table 14 - Table 16 present the simulated energy savings for the improved efficiency characteristics of the traction components.

Table 14: Simulation results for improved traction component efficiencies for HS250 service

	HS250 – baseline	HS250 – traction component update	Absolute energy difference in kWh	Relative energy difference in %
traction energy of motor converters at DC link in kWh	3380,08	3355,32	24,76	0,73
recuperated energy of motor converters at DC link in kWh*	273,00	275,09	-2,09	-0,77
auxiliary energy at the DC link in kWh	598,43	597,45	0,98	0,16
consumed energy at the catenary in kWh	4413,89	4281,43	132,46	3,00
recuperated energy at the catenary in kWh*	219,96	228,03	-8,07	-3,67
net energy in kWh	4193,92	4053,4	140,52	3,35

* Note: Negative values for absolute/relative energy savings during recuperation imply that a larger amount of braking energy is returned back to the grid.

Table 15: Simulation results improved traction component efficiencies for Reg140 service

	Reg140 – baseline	Reg140 – traction component update	Absolute energy difference in kWh	Relative energy difference in %
traction energy of motor converters at DC link in kWh	332,23	328,86	3,37	1,02
recuperated energy of motor converters at DC link in kWh*	111,51	112,7	-1,20	-1,07
auxiliary energy at the DC link in kWh	179,23	170,38	8,86	4,94
consumed energy at the catenary in kWh	572,10	534,45	37,65	6,58
recuperated energy at the catenary in kWh*	87,59	92,75	-5,16	-5,89
net energy in kWh	484,51	441,7	42,81	8,84

Table 16: Simulation results improved traction component efficiencies for Freight Mainline service

	FrMain – baseline	FrMain – traction component update	Absolute energy difference in kWh	Relative energy difference in %
traction energy of motor converters at DC link in kWh	4876,82	4843,19	33,63	0,69
recuperated energy of motor converters at DC link in kWh*	575,93	582,88	-6,95	-1,21
auxiliary energy at the DC link in kWh	304,38	303,12	1,26	0,41
consumed energy at the catenary in kWh	5740,67	5555,02	185,65	3,23
recuperated energy at the catenary in kWh*	486,33	508,91	-22,58	-4,64
net energy in kWh	5254,34	5046,11	208,23	3,96

Conclusively, the total energy savings are in a range of approx. 3.4% (HS250) up to 8.8% (Reg140) regarding the reference energy consumption due to an energy efficiency improvement of about 3 percentage points for the total traction energy efficiency η_{trac}^E . The highest benefit is observed for the Reg140 service, which may be caused by a high number of acceleration and braking phases during the drive cycle.

* Note: Negative values for absolute/relative energy savings during recuperation imply that a larger amount of braking energy is returned back to the grid.

7.2.1.2 Improvement of traction component efficiencies for DC traction topology

For the group of trains running with DC power supply, the Tram and Metro services are investigated. In contrast to an AC traction chain, for the DC topology only the improvement of the motor converter is considered.

In analogy to the results in the above subsection, the efficiency of the improved motor converter is determined for the total drive cycles by evaluating the input and output power of the motor. The corresponding values are summarized in .

Table 17.

Table 17: Mean values for the updated efficiency of the motor inverters for DC power supply

Service category Efficiency of the components	Metro – baseline	Metro – efficiency update	Tram – baseline	Tram – efficiency update
Gearbox	0,98	0,98	0,98	0,98
Motor	0,451	0,451	0,381	0,381
Motor inverter	0,927	0,955	0,918	0,945
Line inductor	0,962	0,961	0,987	0,987
Total traction chain energy efficiency η_{trac}^E	0,395	0,407	0,339	0,349
Total train energy efficiency η_{total}	0,476	0,481	0,569	0,575
updated values				

Based on the high amount of dwell times at the stations, the motor efficiencies are comparatively low. This effect is alleageable due to the application of idle losses during no load operation.

Furthermore, for the DC traction topology, only an improvement of the motor converter efficiency is considered. The energy savings are consequently smaller in comparison to the AC topology reductions. The effect of the improved efficiency is not very pronounced. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the resulting power profiles. This is also in line with results of deliverable DO5.2, as the total energy losses of the motor converter accounted only for 9.73% and 9.53% of total energy losses for the tram and metro services respectively.

Nevertheless, the energy savings for the total drive cycle are stated in Table 18 and Table 19. Here, an energy saving of about 1% is achieved due to an energy efficiency improvement approx. 2.7 percentage points of the motor converter characteristic.

Table 18: Simulation results improved traction component efficiencies for Metro service

	Metro – baseline	Metro – traction component update	Absolute energy difference in kWh	Relative energy difference in %
traction energy of motor converters at DC link in kWh	313,80	311,10	2,70	0,86
recuperated energy of motor converters at DC link in kWh*	170,14	171,69	-1,56	-0,91
auxiliary energy at the DC link in kWh	114,19	115,78	-1,60	-1,40
consumed energy at the catenary in kWh	419,57	417,84	1,73	0,41
recuperated energy at the catenary in kWh*	151,52	152,46	-0,95	-0,63
net energy in kWh	268,06	265,38	2,68	1,00

Table 19: Simulation results improved traction component efficiencies for Tram service

	Tram – baseline	Tram – traction component update	Absolute energy difference in kWh	Relative energy difference in %
traction energy of motor converters at DC link in kWh	38,67	38,34	0,34	0,87
recuperated energy of motor converters at DC link in kWh*	18,87	19,09	-0,22	-1,18
auxiliary energy at the DC link in kWh	33,33	33,33	0,00	0,00
consumed energy at the catenary in kWh	68,57	68,23	0,34	0,50
recuperated energy at the catenary in kWh*	14,74	14,96	-0,22	-1,49
net energy in kWh	53,83	53,27	0,56	1,04

* Note: Negative values for absolute/relative energy savings during recuperation imply that a larger amount of braking energy is returned back to the grid.

7.2.2 Improvement of gearbox efficiencies for High Speed service

This subsection focuses on the improvements of the gearbox efficiency for the HS300 and the HS250 service. The improved efficiency, which is the basis for the following simulations, is summarized in Table 20 below.

Table 20: Efficiency improvements of the gearbox

	HS300	HS250
Baseline efficiency	98 %	98 %
Efficiency improvements⁺ <small>*according to TD 1.1</small>	1 %	1 %
New efficiency	99 %	99 %

Despite the adjusted gearbox efficiency, the simulations are evaluated with the baseline setting of the HS300 and HS250 service. Therefore, also the baseline speed profile is utilized for the following simulations.

The simulation results, which are summarized in Table 21 and Table 22, show the energy savings at different levels of the traction chain - at the wheel, at the intermediate circuit and at the catenary.

Table 21: Simulation results for improved gearbox efficiency for HS300 service

	HS300- baseline	HS300 – gearbox update	Absolute energy difference in kWh	Relative energy difference in %
traction energy of motor converters at DC link in kWh	4015,80	3976,56	1,36	0,98
recuperated energy of motor converters at DC link in kWh*	100,04	101,07	47,48	-1,03
auxiliary energy at the DC link in kWh	553,08	551,72	-0,85	0,25
consumed energy at the catenary in kWh	5135,92	5088,44	48,33	0,92
recuperated energy at the catenary in kWh*	80,89	81,74	-0,85	- 1,05
net energy in kWh	5055,03	5006,70	48,33	0,95

* Note: Negative values for absolute/relative energy savings during recuperation imply that a larger amount of braking energy is returned back to the grid

Table 22: Simulation results for improved gearbox efficiency for HS250 service

	HS250- baseline	HS250 – gearbox update	Absolute energy difference in kWh	Relative energy difference in %
traction energy of motor converters at DC link in kWh	3380,08	3349,48	30,60	0,91
recuperated energy of motor converters at DC link in kWh*	273,00	275,84	-2,83	-1,04
auxiliary energy at the DC link in kWh	598,43	597,54	0,89	0,15
consumed energy at the catenary in kWh	4413,89	4377,59	36,30	0,82
recuperated energy at the catenary in kWh*	219,96	222,41	-2,45	-1,11
net energy in kWh	4193,92	4155,17	38,75	0,92

For the implementation of a more efficient gearbox with an efficiency improvement of 1 percentage point, an energy saving of about 1% for the total net energy is achieved.

7.3 Simulation of combined technical innovations for High Speed service

In this subsection, the technical innovations presented in subsections 7.1 and 7.2 are combined to analyse the total possible energy saving potential. As the major weight reduction as well as the improved gearbox efficiency are only investigated for the high speed service, the combination of the technical innovations are implemented for the HS300 and HS250 service. The major improvement for the other service categories, which is investigated in this report is already covered by the converter/transformer improvement, which is described in subsection 7.2.

The simulation results are shown in Table 23 and Table 24. Here, a total energy saving of about 5% of the reference energy consumption is achieved by combining the innovations presented in subsection 7.1 and 7.2.

Table 23: Simulation results combined technical innovations (reduced weight, improved efficiency for gearbox and converters/transformers) for HS300 service

	HS300 – baseline	HS300 – total update	Absolute energy difference in kWh	Relative energy difference in %
traction energy at the wheel in kWh	3502,63	3499,11	3,52	0,10
total braking energy at the wheel in kWh	153,59	149,92	3,67	2,39
traction energy of motor converters at DC link in kWh	4015,80	3945,01	70,79	1,76
recuperated energy of motor converters at DC link in kWh*	100,04	102,00	-1,96	-1,96
auxiliary energy at the DC link in kWh	553,08	550,49	2,59	0,47
consumed energy at the catenary in kWh	5135,92	4885,34	250,58	4,88
recuperated energy at the catenary in kWh*	80,89	84,89	-4,00	-4,94
net energy in kWh	5055,03	4800,45	254,58	5,04

Table 24: Simulation results combined technical innovations (reduced weight, improved efficiency for gearbox and converters/transformers) for HS250 service

	HS250 – baseline	HS250 – total update	Absolute energy difference in kWh	Relative energy difference in %
traction energy at the wheel in kWh	2850,94	2794,77	56,17	1,97
total braking energy at the wheel in kWh	654,71	594,49	60,23	9,20
traction energy of motor converters at DC link in kWh	3380,08	3262,44	117,64	3,48
recuperated energy of motor converters at DC link in kWh*	273,00	256,12	16,88	6,18
auxiliary energy at the DC link in kWh	598,43	593,91	4,52	0,75
consumed energy at the catenary in kWh	4413,89	4179,33	234,56	5,31
recuperated energy at the catenary in kWh*	219,96	212,07	7,89	3,59
net energy in kWh	4193,92	3967,25	226,67	5,40

* Note: Negative values for absolute/relative energy savings during recuperation imply that a bigger amount of braking energy is returned back to the grid

8 Conclusion and Outlook

This deliverable report presents simulation results evaluated with technical innovations of single Shift2Rail technical demonstrators. As a basis for these simulations, several train parameter updates, representing innovative technologies, were gathered by the FINE1 energy group. In analogy to [2] and [3], the simulation results were evaluated in order to assess the influence of the technical innovations.

To explain the utilized parameters for the single simulations, the theoretical background underlying the investigated technical innovations is explained. Furthermore, the baseline scenario is presented and the baseline results are summarised. The evaluated simulation results of the investigated techniques are compared to the baseline results in order to assess the influence regarding the in-vehicle energy usage. Additionally, this report underlines the sensitivity analysis, which is under investigation in deliverable DO5.2.

Finally, this report contributes to a global vision of energy usage in railways, developed in OPEUS WP7, as well as to an evaluation of energy key performance indicators in FINE1 WP4.

9 References

- [1] H. Völker, „FINE1 Deliverable D4.4 - Data gathering from S2R TDs,“ EU-project FINE1 (S2R-CFM-CCA-02-2015), 2019.
- [2] L. Pröhl, „OPEUS Deliverable DO3.3 - S2R innovation (state01) simulation results and periodic assessment - Part1,“ EU-project OPEUS (S2R-OC-CCA-02-2015), 2018.
- [3] L. Pröhl, „OPEUS Deliverable DO3.3 - S2R innovation (state01) simulation results and periodic assessment - Part2,“ EU-project OPEUS (S2R-OC-CCA-02-2015), 2018.
- [4] L. Pröhl, „OPEUS Deliverable - DO2.3 OPEUS simulation tool manual,“ EU-project OPEUS (S2R-OC-CCA-02-2015), 2017.
- [5] L. Pröhl, „OPEUS Deliverable DO2.1 - OPEUS simulation methodology,“ EU-project OPEUS (S2R-OC-CCA-02-2015), 2017.
- [6] R. Palacin, „OPEUS Deliverable DO3.1 - Scenario set up and discription,“ EU-project OPEUS (S2R-OC-CCA-02-2015), 2017.
- [7] J. Ernst, „FINE1 Deliverable D3.1 - Energy baseline,“ EU-project FINE1 (S2R-CFM-CCA-02-2015), 2018.
- [8] L. Pröhl, „OPEUS Deliverable DO3.2 - Baseline simulation results and assessment,“ EU-project OPEUS (S2R-OC-CCA-02-2015), 2018.
- [9] H. Dittus, „FINE1 Deliverable D3.4 - Requirement specification for energy simulation tool,“ EU-project FINE1 (S2R-CFM-CCA-02-2015), 2017.
- [10] M. Marsilla, „OPEUS Deliverable DO5.2 - Analysis of energy losses in the traction chain,“ EU-project OPEUS (S2R-OC-CCA-02-2015), 2019.